

ALGORITHM FOR SEASONALLY ADJUSTABLE RESERVOIR MODELING AND
DEVELOPMENT OF A MATHEMATICAL MODEL

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7857799>

Abstract. Our article demonstrates creating the mathematical models and modelling algorithms for regulated watersourses.

Keywords: algorithm, seasonally, modeling.

The Hisorak reservoir is designed to provide water storage for the irrigation of Kashkadarya region. The reservoir has a rock dam with a maximum height of 140 m and a crest length of 528 m. The intake facility is located in the dam, and the deep operating water flow is located in the middle of the dam [1].

The dynamics of water in the reservoir in time can be described by the differential equation of the following form:

$$x(k+1) = f(x(k), u(k), \theta, k) + g(\theta, x(k))w(k), x(k_0) = x_0, \quad (1)$$

Here $x(k) \in R^2$ - vector state, ($x_1(k)$ - the volume of water in the reservoir, $x_2(k)$ - water level in the reservoir); $u(k) \in R^3$ - control effect vector, ($u_1(k)$ - consumption of water entering the reservoir; $u_2(k)$ - the amount of water released from the reservoir; $u_3(k)$ - amount of water consumption); $\theta \in R^s$ - unknown vector of parameters; x_0 - the initial volume of the reservoir at the present time k_0 ; f and g - some functions; $w(k)$ - a sequence of Gaussian random variables with zero mean and covariance

$$E\{w(k)w^T(j)\} = Q(k)\delta_{kj}.$$

Initial state x_0 - covariance P_0 and \bar{x}_0 is also a random variable with a mean. Optimizing reservoir operation modes consists in choosing such control measures in the water release structure, according to which the water supply schedule is provided, and at the same time, water losses for evaporation and filtration from the surface of the reservoir are minimal [2].

In the process of filling the water reservoir, the control functions are the consumption of water input $u_1(t)$, water output $u_2(t)$ and water consumption $u_3(t)$ and - the working process of the water reservoir.

Object state constraints [3] have the form:

$$H_{\min} \leq h(t) \leq H_{\max}, \\ dh(t)/dt \leq U_{kp},$$

here: $h(t)$ - water level in the reservoir; H_{\min}, H_{\max} - respectively, the minimum and maximum permissible value of the ordinate of the free water level in the reservoir; U_{kp} critical value of reservoir filling and operating speed.

(1) To linearize equation, we use the extended Kalman filter [3], as a result of which we get

$$x(k+1) = A(\theta, k)x(k) + B(\theta, k)u(k) + G(k)w(k), \quad (2)$$

$$y(k) = C(\theta, k)x(k) + \eta(k),$$

here $A(\theta, k), B(\theta, k)$ and $C(\theta, k)$ – linear functions of the unknown parameter vector θ of dimension, $\eta(k)$ – is a sequence of Gaussian random variables with zero mean and covariance.

$$x(k+1) = A(k, \theta)x(k) + B(k, \theta)u(k) + G(k)w(k) = D(k)u(k) + G(k)w(k)$$

(3)

here $D(k)$ – from the function $x(k)$ and $u(k)$. Assuming $\hat{\theta}(k/k)$ had a guess θ for k at the given time X^k , x and θ from conventional estimation procedures to obtain one-step estimates of [4] can be used.

$$\hat{x}(k+1/k) = \hat{A}(k/k, \hat{\theta})x(k) + \hat{B}(k/k, \hat{\theta})u(k)$$

Recurrent parameter estimation and error covariance $\Gamma(k+1/k+1)$ defined by the following expressions:

$$\hat{\theta}(k+1/k+1) = \hat{\theta}(k+1/k) + K(k+1)P^{-1}(k+1/k)[x(k+1) - \hat{x}(k+1/k)],$$

$$K(k+1) = F(k)\Gamma(k/k)D^T(k),$$

$$\Gamma(k+1/k+1) = \Gamma(k+1/k) - K(k+1)P^{-1}(k+1/k)K^T(k+1).$$

Now we can write the control algorithm using the optimal system synthesis method [4] to minimize the average value of the quality criterion in the following form:

$$J(U_k^{N-1}) = E \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=k}^{N-1} x^T(i+1)M(i)x(i+1) + u^T(i)N(i)u(i) \middle| Z^k, U^k \right\}, \quad (4)$$

here $M(i) = M^T(i) \geq 0$ and $N(i) = N^T(i) > 0$.

To find the sequence U_{k+1}^{N-1} , Considering (3), we use the method of minimizing (4), dynamic optimization [4]:

$$u^*(j/k) = -C(j/k)x(j), \quad j = k+1, \dots, N-1,$$

$$C(j/k) = [E\{B^T(j, \theta)S(j+1/k)B(j, \theta) + R(j)\}]^{-1} \times E\{B^T(j)S(j+1/k)A(j, \theta)\}, \quad (5)$$

$$S(j/k) = E\{[A(j, \theta) - B(j, \theta)C(j/k)]^T (M(j) + S(j+1/k)) \times [A(j, k) - B(j, \theta)C(j/k)] + C(j/k)N(j)C^T(j/k)\}.$$

The above formalization of the process allows choosing the structure of the mathematical model in the following form:

$$x_{k+1} = A_k x_k + B_k u_k + w_k, \quad x_{k_0} = x_0,$$

$$y_k = C_k x_k + \eta_k, \quad k \in \{k_0, k_1, \dots, k_T\},$$

here

$$A_k = \begin{bmatrix} a_{11,k} & a_{12,k} \\ a_{21,k} & a_{22,k} \end{bmatrix}, B_k = \begin{bmatrix} b_{11,k} & b_{12,k} & b_{13,k} \\ b_{21,k} & b_{22,k} & b_{23,k} \end{bmatrix}, C_k = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

$$M[x_0] = 0, M[x_0 x_0^T] = X_0, M[\eta_k] = 0, M[x_0 \eta_k^T] = 0, M[x_0 w_k^T] = 0,$$

$$M \begin{bmatrix} w_k \\ \eta_k \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} w_i^T & \eta_i^T \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} W & G \\ G^T & V \end{bmatrix} \delta_{k-i}.$$

Then the process and observation equations are written in the following form:

$$x_{k+1} = A_k x_k + B_k u_k + w_k, \quad x_{k_0} = x_0, \quad (7)$$

$$\theta_{k+1} = \theta_k + w_k^\theta, \quad (8)$$

$$y_k = C_k x_k + \eta_k, \quad (9)$$

Advanced vector state input $x^p = [x^T | \theta^T]^T$, (7)-(8) we write the equations in the following form

$$x_{k+1}^p = f^p[x_k^p, u_k, k] + w_k^p,$$

$$z_{k+1} = c[x_k^p, u_k, k] + w_k,$$

$$\text{here: } x_k^p = \begin{bmatrix} x_k \\ \theta_k \end{bmatrix}, f^p = \begin{bmatrix} f[x_k, \theta_k, u_k, k] \\ \theta_k \end{bmatrix}, w_k^p = \begin{bmatrix} w_k \\ w_k^\theta \end{bmatrix}.$$

The required values of the registration and discretization time of the implementation of the observed random processes turned out to be equal, respectively: $T = 30$ hours, $\Delta t = 20$ min. A total of 90 measurements were taken.

To estimate the extended state vector $x^{pT} = [x^T | \theta^T]$ simple algorithms of the object in question are used. Analysis of state variables and parameter vector setting processes shows that the required variables have acceptable accuracy and convergence speed.

The parameters of the model turned out to be equal:

$$A_k = \begin{bmatrix} 0.625 & 0.375 \\ 0.189 & 0.801 \end{bmatrix}, B_k = \begin{bmatrix} 0.627 & 0.317 \\ 0.185 & -0.962 \end{bmatrix}, C_k = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix},$$

To determine the appropriateness of the developed models, we use a criterion based on the analysis of the properties of the residuals and related to the verification of assumptions about the model. The maximum value of the empirical correlation calculated for the residuals was equal to 0.174.

Since this value is less than the critical value, $2/(N)1/2 = 2/(90)1/2 = 0.21$, the hypothesis of independence of residuals can be considered consistent with the initial data, that is, the developed model adequately describes the process under consideration in the field of experience and can be used to develop a control system.

Summary. The developed mathematical model of the reservoir allows establishing quantitative relationships between the main input and output variables, predicting the state of the process with existing or selected control elements, and synthesizing optimal adaptive control laws for the considered process.

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